

Assessment of Awareness on Antenatal Care Service Delivery among Pregnant Women in North-West, Nigeria

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to assess awareness of antenatal care service delivery among pregnant women in North-West, Nigeria. To achieve this purpose, the ex-post facto research design was adopted for the study. The population for the study comprised of pregnant women in all the seven (7) states in North-west, Nigeria within the year 2023. Estimated at one million two hundred and twenty-three thousand, five hundred and seventy-one (1,223,571). The sample size for this study consists of 768 pregnant women. The participants were selected using multi-stage sampling techniques. Close-ended questionnaire titled “awareness of antenatal care service delivery among pregnant women” with reliability index (Cronbach Alpha) of 0.859 was used to obtain responses from the respondents. Descriptive statistics of frequencies, percentages, means and standard deviation were used to describe the demographic characteristics of the respondents and to answer the research question. Hypothesis formulated was tested at 0.05 level of significance using one sample t-test. The finding revealed that the pregnant women in North-west zone, Nigeria have no significant awareness of antenatal care services ($p = 0.12$). Thus, it is concluded that pregnant women in North West zone, Nigeria have inadequate awareness on antenatal care service. On the basis of the conclusion the study further recommends that: There should be a practical demonstration of the antenatal talk by health educators to pregnant women as it relates to antenatal care services.

Keyword: awareness, antenatal, pregnant women, antenatal care service delivery.

Introduction

Antenatal care is a medical and general care that is provided to pregnant women during pregnancy and it is goal-oriented provided with the aim of meeting both psychological and medical needs of pregnant women within the context of health care delivery system. The major aim of antenatal care is to ensure that the mother reaches the end of pregnancy as healthy as, or even healthier than she was before the pregnancy (Federal Ministry of Health {FMOH}, 2014). Researches reveal that in many pregnancies there are relatively high proportion of complications and some of which are very serious and of a life-threatening nature (Tochi, *et al* 2022). Good care during pregnancy is important for the health of the mother and the development of the unborn baby. Pregnancy is a crucial time to promote healthy behaviours and parenting skills (Haruna, 2017). Good ANC links the woman and her family with the formal health system, increases the chance of using a skilled attendant at birth and contributes to good health through the life cycle. Inadequate care during this time breaks a critical link in the continuum of care, and affects both mothers and their babies. The World Health Organization (2016), recommends a minimum of eight ANC visits for every pregnant woman and to have their first contact in the first twelve weeks' gestation with subsequent contacts taking place at 20, 26, 30, 34, 36, 38 and 40 weeks of gestation.

Assessment of Awareness on Antenatal ... (Muhammad, et. al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10642361>

Nigeria is Africa's most populous country with a population of over 140 million people (National Demographic and Health Survey {NDHS}, 2017). It is reported that, there are about 31 million women of childbearing age (Abimbola et al., 2017). Maternal mortality is estimated to be more than twice as high in the rural areas (828 deaths per 100,000 live births) than in the urban areas (351 deaths per 100,000 live births) (Abimbola et al., 2017). Zonal variations abound in maternal mortality figures across Nigeria. WHO (2021), reports that maternal mortality rates (MMR) are significantly higher in Northern Nigeria compared to the Southern part of the country. The North West zones with MMR of 1,549 deaths per 100,000 live births and 1,025 deaths per 100,000 live births with a rate of about ten and six times higher than that in the South West (165 deaths per 100,000 live-births) (Adegoke et al., 2017).

North-West zone, is known for poor health care system, inadequate maternal and child health care, illiteracy and poor socio-economic status (National Demographic and Health Survey {NDHS}, 2017). United State Agency for International Development {USAID}, (2016), reported that North West zone of Nigeria like other geo-political zones in Nigeria has formulated strategies such as primary health care program, which, however, faces tremendous challenges in achieving national wide coverage on maternal and child birth care. It is observed that in some states in North West zone of Nigeria, an estimated 200,000 babies die as stillbirths during their last twelve weeks of pregnancy. It is estimated that babies who die before the onset of labour, or ante partum stillbirths, account for two-thirds of all stillbirths in some states where the mortality rate is greater than 22 per 100 births – nearly all states in Nigeria (Medical Center Health System {MCHS}, 2015).

Objectives of the study

The main purpose of this study was to assess the awareness on antenatal care service delivery among pregnant women in North-West zone, Nigeria.

Research Questions

What is the level of awareness of pregnant women on antenatal care service delivery in northwest Nigeria?

Hypotheses

There is no significant difference between awareness and antenatal care service delivery among pregnant women in North-west Nigeria.

Methodology

Ex-post facto research design was used for this study; this is also referred to as after-the-fact research design. Sharma, (2019), explained that in the context of social science research an ex-post facto investigation seeks to reveal possible relationships by observing an existing condition or state of affairs and searching back in time for plausible contributing factors. The population for this study comprised of all pregnant women in the seven (7) states of North-West zone, mount to one million two hundred and twenty-three thousand, five hundred and seventy-one (1,223,571) (National Bureau of Statistic, 2022). The sample size for the study consisted of 768 pregnant mothers drawn from the total population using multistage sampling technique. Stratified sampling technique was used to divide the zone into three strata as already done by FMOH (2021), on the basis of proximity, in which a stratum consisted of two (2) states with the exception of the 3rd stratum which consisted of three (3) States. Namely: Jigawa and Kaduna as first stratum, Kano and Katsina as second stratum, while Sokoto, Kebbi and Zamfara as third stratum. Three (3) states were selected from their various strata using simple random sampling technique. The same technique was employed in selecting senatorial zone within the selected states, local Governments areas and Heath facilities used in this study. To compute the number of respondents in each selected LGA and healthcare facility, a proportionate sampling technique was used. This technique was used to give equal chance of been selected to each respondent. Systematic sampling technique was used to select respondents from each of the health facility selected. The research instrument used for this study was a closed ended questionnaire titled: "Awareness on antenatal care service delivery among pregnant women". The questionnaire consists of two (2) sections: section A; contained three (3) statements on personal data of the respondents. Section B; contained ten (10) statements on knowledge of antenatal care service among pregnant mothers in North-West zone, Nigeria. To ascertain the reliability of the instrument used in this study, a pilot study was conducted. Two health facilities were randomly selected because they formed part of the population of the health facilities in North West zone, Nigeria. In each of these selected sampled health facilities, twenty (20) questionnaires were purposively administered to 20 pregnant women who attended two health facilities on Tuesday and Thursday. Hence, a total of 40 questionnaires were purposively administered to 40 respondents. The copies of questionnaire were retrieved on the spot and processed for reliability through Cronbach Alpha. The results revealed that reliability was 0.859, the instrument is considered reliable. Taber (2018), state that acceptable reliability of an instrument is 0.50. Descriptive statistics of frequency, percentages, mean score and standard deviation were

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used to describe the demographic characteristics and to answer the research question. Inferential statistics of one sample t-test was used to test the null hypothesis.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the level of awareness of pregnant women on antenatal care service delivery in northwest Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean Scores of Responses on knowledge of ANC Services among Pregnant women in North-West Zone, Nigeria

S/no	Statement	Mean	SD
1	I am aware of HIV screening during ANC clinic in the hospitals	2.25	1.06
2	I have good understanding of the benefits of weight measuring during ANC clinic in the hospital	2.05	1.07
3	I am aware of regular checking of blood pressure during ANC clinics	2.52	1.43
4	Respiratory rate measurement for the pregnant mothers during ANC clinic services is known by me	2.59	1.22
5	I am aware of hepatitis B virus screening during ANC clinics	2.37	1.23
6	I am aware of immunization with tetanus toxoid vaccine during ANC visit	2.56	1.21
7	I have good understanding of blood sugar level test during ANC visit	2.28	1.19
8	I am informed about blood screening for malaria during ANC visit	2.46	1.17
9	I am aware of ultrasound scanning during ANC visit	2.31	1.12
10	I am aware of urine test for protein and blood glucose during ANC visit	2.12	1.10
TOTAL		2.35	1.16

Field work (2022)

Observation of Table 1 shows that the respondents revealed that they are not knowledgeable about antenatal care services as most of the mean scores of responses were less than 2.50, except items 3, 4, and 6 where the means score of responses were 2.50 and slightly above. Know about checking of blood pressure (2.52; 1.43), respiratory rate measurement (2.59; 1.22), and immunization with tetanus toxoid vaccine (2.56; 1.21). The aggregate mean score of 2.35 indicates that pregnant mothers in North West zone of Nigeria are not knowledgeable of antenatal care services.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between awareness and antenatal care service delivery among pregnant women in North-west Nigeria.

Table 2: One sample t-test Analysis on awareness of ANC Services among Pregnant women of in North-West zone, Nigeria

Variable	Mean	Std.	Df	t-value	P-value.
awareness	2.351	1.157	9	40.553	0.12

$t(9) = 1.833$ $P < 0.05$ Significant.

The result shows the t-value of 40.553 at 9 degree of freedom (df) and a significance level of 0.12 at 0.05 level of confidence, with this result indeed supports the hypothesis which states that “pregnant women do not have significant awareness of ANC services in North West zone of Nigeria”. The hypothesis was therefore retained. Thus, there is no significant difference between awareness and antenatal care service delivery among pregnant women in North-west Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The primary purpose of this study was to assess the awareness on antenatal care service delivery among pregnant women in North-West zone, Nigeria. To achieve this purpose, it became necessary to assess the level of the awareness on antenatal care service delivery among pregnant women in North-West zone, Nigeria. The findings of this study revealed that pregnant women in North West zone of Nigeria does not have significant awareness on Antenatal care service delivery with a p-value of 0.12. This finding is in consonance with Gurmesa (2015), who reported that pregnant mothers are not knowledgeable

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of antenatal care services, it could be in realization that knowledge of pregnant mothers is a major factor in determining the extent to which antenatal care services are used. Ibrahim (2020), identified factors associated with late antenatal care attendance in selected rural and urban communities in Kebbi state, that inadequate awareness about antenatal care services resulted into 2.2 times high odds for late antenatal care attendance than women who had adequate knowledge in urban cities. The perception of no benefits derived from commencement of antenatal care early was associated with four times likelihood of late attendance in the urban city (WHO, 2017). According to Raru, Ayana, Zakaria and Merga, (2022), levels of education and knowledge were the most important predictors of antenatal care utilization. The study revealed that antenatal care utilization was relatively low in East African countries. This study also depicts that a higher level of maternal formal education significantly increases the utilization of antenatal care services, even after controlling for other socioeconomic factors. Furthermore, with respect to knowledge of ANC services, Andualalem, Hamel, Hana and Hale (2015), opined that 11.8% of the respondents did not know about antenatal care, the result was lower with El-Sherbini (2018) in Assiut General Hospital which was 25.5%. The researcher observed that this difference could be attributable to difference in population (304) and time of study in which the present population was 768 and the other reason is difference in operational definition. But their result was comparable with the result of Ibrahim (2020), 14.5% have no knowledge of antenatal care services among pregnant mothers in Nigeria and 73% of pregnant mothers in Zurmi general hospital lacked basic and essential knowledge about antenatal care. Okonofua et al., (2018), found that antenatal care nonattendance rate by pregnant women is high with about 62.1%, and a skilled delivery of 46.6% by recently delivered women at PHCs, while 25% of women delivered at home or with traditional birth attendants. There were several reasons for use and non-use of PHCs for antenatal and delivery care given by women some related to perceptions about long distances to PHCs, high costs of services and poor quality of PHC service delivery. The study also opined that the use of PHC facility was less among women who had low autonomy (OR 0.75, CI 0.57–0.99) as compared to women with higher autonomy. Additionally, Mohammed (2019) reported that 58.2% of the pregnant women had unsatisfactory knowledge about antenatal care service.

Conclusion

On the basis of the research findings, it is concluded that, there is no significant difference between awareness and antenatal care service delivery among pregnant women in North-west Nigeria.

Recommendations

The following are recommendations made as a result of the finding of the study:

1. There should be a practical demonstration of the antenatal talk by health educators to the pregnant women as this may improve their knowledge concerning antenatal care services.
2. There is need for the antenatal talk to be more of an interactive session between the nurses and the pregnant women, so that the pregnant mothers can discuss their doubts about any confusing matter and also ask questions regarding the aspects of the talk that is not clear to them.

Acknowledgements

The researchers' deepest gratitude goes to Almighty Allah for His protection, provision, mercies and guidance throughout the duration of this study, and for enabling them to complete this work. The researchers wish to express their indebtedness to their family members for their understanding, prayers and all kind of contributions. The researchers are most grateful to the entire staff of the Department of Human Kinetics and health Education, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria, especially the Head of Department (Prof. Umaru Musa) and Prof. (Mrs) M.A Suleiman.

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